

MATERIALS SCIENCE AND MECHANICS OF MACHINES

ORGANIZATION OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT DRIVERS' OPERATIONS BY THE SECTORAL METHOD

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Abstract

The issues of reducing the cost of passenger transportation and improving the efficiency of route passenger transport are still relevant for enterprises that carry passengers in regular traffic on established routes. The solution of these issues is possible by choosing the passenger capacity of the vehicles used, assigning traffic intervals in accordance with the current volume of passenger traffic, transforming the existing route network, changing the routes of routes and their modes of operation. An alternative way is to reduce the cost of passenger transportation by improving the quality of the organization of operational work of the enterprise using a rational mode of using drivers' working hours. The spectral method, which allows achieving results in this direction by combining drivers into sectors, is considered in this article

Keywords: Sectoral method, buses, trolleybuses, trams, efficiency improvement, rational distribution of driver's resource.

1. Introduction

A certain traditionally used group of methods of organizing the shift work of drivers of public transport provide for the assignment of drivers to permanent routes. The study of the shifts time fund in the context of routes shows a significant heterogeneity of the latter, which, if a driver is assigned to a permanent route, leads to an increase in unproductive costs, which are associated with an irrational distribution of driving time. Tasks, at first glance, with similar content are known as planning tasks (planning), work schedules (crew scheduling) and shift placement (rostering).

However, in most cases, these tasks, due to the general approach, do not take into account the peculiarities of route passenger transport and the organization of work of drivers who serve passenger transport routes. The work of these drivers differs in the performance of certain volumes, while drivers can be assigned to one vehicle and must replace each other. Drivers' working hours are also normalized and influenced by a number of factors and circumstances of the operation of route passenger transport. In this regard, it is interesting to solve this problem based on the principles of operation of route passenger transport and in the field of maintenance of operational enterprises.

A distinctive feature of the formulation of the problem for route passenger transport is the necessary flexibility and interchangeability of drivers on serviced routes (groups of routes). At the same time, the peculiarity of the task is the variability of the composition of

drivers due to a greater degree of staff turnover and the employment of new ones. The situation on the drivers' labor market is still very difficult, so it is very difficult to talk about long-term prospects. At the same time, for the purposes of medium- and short-term planning, we must have a universal criterion and method that will allow us to reduce unproductive costs by preparing production in such a way as to make it universal.

It is possible to increase the rationality of the use of drivers' working hours when working by the sectoral method. The sectoral method provides for the work of enterprise drivers assigned not to routes, but to sectors. The work of drivers within the sector is organized in such a way that, alternating within the sector between shifts assigned to it, drivers develop an equal standard of working time without significant deviations, which leads to a reduction in unproductive costs. Due to the heterogeneity of the distribution of the duration of shifts on routes, an objective indicator characterizing the sector is the weighted average duration of the driver's work on shifts assigned to the sector, taking into account the sets of shifts that differ in characteristic days of the week and the number of these days in the period under consideration.

The task of forming sectors at routes transports enterprises when using the sectoral method is reduced to such an optimal division of the shifts existing at the enterprise by the sectors being created, in which the value of the weighted average duration of work in each formed sector will differ slightly between sectors, while

in each formed sector there should be at least a threshold value of shifts ending before 24:00 (further — "special shift"), to provide drivers with them before their day off [1]. The task is original in that the division is carried out under the control of equality of the weighted average value of the shift duration in each formed sector with a number of restrictions with an unknown number of sectors and the number of shifts in them.

The relevance of this task for the direction of the organization of public transport is high.

At the same time, the task is not only in the plane of the process of organizing passenger transportation, but also affects some related areas. In particular, in the field of economics, this task solves the issues of overspending resources due to irrationally planned runs (fuel, electric energy, maintenance and repair), overspending on workers' wages due to the need to pay for unproductive work time, irrational use of human resources (on some days not everyone is involved for work, on other days they are involved additional resources).

In the field of traffic safety, the task is relevant from the point of view of the duration of continuous work, the impact of monotony when working on a constant route, awareness and awareness of drivers when they quickly switch from route to route.

In environmental matters, this task is associated with the elimination of irrational mileage, which causes additional fuel consumption and electrical energy, which generates excess CO₂ emissions.

The prerequisites, research and development of the sectoral method are presented in the following sections of this article.

2. References Review

The issues of organizing the work of drivers are presented in the research. Authors Mingming Chen and Huimin Niu of the article [2] consider the issues of modeling the work of bus drivers through a multi-approach to the implementation of individual flights on routes. This may be applicable in those cities and countries where there is no rigid attachment of the driver to the group of routes served and to the vehicle. The main goal of the work is to achieve such a combination of flights that will minimize downtime. Similar approaches are considered by the authors [3] and other authors. But such approaches are not applicable in for example Belarus, where a different system of work has been adopted. Planning tasks [4, 5, 6] most often consider the distribution of work shifts by days of the month and the distribution of drivers by these shifts, but they do not match the working day and the duration of this working day, which can be variable from route to route. Well-known rostering tasks consider solutions with the binding and distribution of specific drivers in the already prevailing conditions of the month, but not more often in a universal system, where one driver's place can safely be occupied by another (due to his transition or dismissal). Sergio A. Useche, Viviola Gómez, Boris Cendales, Francisco Alonso in their work [7], they showed on a large statistical material that stress at work is a problem that jeopardizes the safety of professional drivers and provided evidence confirming the significant impact of workload on the performance of a

professional driver. Przystupa, K., Gil, L., Niewczas, A., Pieniak, D in their publication [8], they show the relevance of the problem of organizing the work of professional drivers from the point of view of considering the problem of work and rest regime as the drivers themselves see it and emphasize the influence of constant work on the driver's attention and reaction when driving a vehicle. Claudio Marcelo Brunoro, Laerte Idal Sznelwar, Ivan Bolis, Julia Abrahao [9] shows how a route passenger transport company can support a policy that can combine the quality of transport with working conditions compatible with professional development, comfort and health of professional drivers and emphasize the urgency of the problem of scheduling drivers' work schedules. In this regard, the studies obtained in [10] are also interesting. S Fores, L Proll & A Wren (2002) in the article [11], discussing the problem of planning the work of a route passenger transport driver, they consider it as a mathematical problem of integer linear programming and heuristics to solve it. Renato & Festa De Leone, Emilia dh Paola & Marchitto in paper [12] also offers a mathematical approach to solving the problem of work planning. The authors in the article [13] show the results of a study that analyzed the work of bus drivers of a public transport company, which is considered a benchmark in its field of activity, in which it strives to achieve operational excellence and emphasize the relevance of issues of planning and scheduling drivers based on the work and rest regime and the influence of psychophysiological characteristics on the success of work. Similar conclusions were also obtained by the authors of [14]. Yindong Shen, Jingpeng Li and Kunkun Peng in [15], it is argued that planning the work of public transport drivers is the process of choosing a set of responsibilities for vehicle drivers in order to form a number of legitimate driver shifts and call for approaching the problem by generating a large set of possible shifts using heuristics specific to a specific subject area, and then selecting a subset to form the final work schedule the method of integer programming. This problem remains no less urgent due to the development of the COVID-19 pandemic, which is confirmed by Bauer, M., Dźwigoń, W., Richter M. [16].

A note to the above described analysis of the problem is the process management of public transport companies itself, where various mathematical methods, methods of operational analysis or the use of knowledge from probability theory are used to optimize the critical tasks of operation. It is also important to perceive the constantly developing science of computer science and to make use of its latest possibilities. Many different analyses have already been carried out on the shortcomings of effective traffic management [17]. All such changes within processes must be subordinated to the communication and information capabilities of the elements and their communications with each other at both horizontal and vertical levels [18]. The goal of process management is to standardize processes, i.e. to set a uniform level of service and performance and to clearly define the responsibilities and competencies of functional positions [19]. The principle of a process management system usually has a straightforward

structure. The individual activities within the process are interrelated and it is not possible to implement specific activities without the condition that those activities are completed which must be followed up. If their interconnectedness in the process is more complex, i.e. there is not just a straight linear sequence of activities within the process, all the interactions of these activities must be taken into account. Focusing on process management is one of the fundamental goals of reengineering. It can also be used to redesign existing processes or to create new processes in the area of transport service provision. The main motive for the application of process management is to improve the level of existing processes, and the way to achieve this is to analyse the processes as a whole. Another factor may be the lack of communication between the different entities ensuring the implementation of processes [20]. However, this is a subject for further analysis and analysis of the issue, which is not the subject of this paper.

3. Data collection

The research was planned and consists of five stages. At the first stage of research was carried out: identification of the problems at the enterprises of route passenger transport, determining of trends, features of operation when using various types of route passenger transport, developing of characteristics of route network, establishment of nomenclature of indicators characterizing the parameters of the routes, statistical processing of research results. At the second stage, a mathematical model of the operation of the vehicle on the route was developed, an experiment was planned to determine the reliability of this model in the conditions of transport operation in a city of 2 million residents. At the third stage, a mathematical model of the driver's work on the route was developed and a generalized criterion was introduced that characterizes each route, an experiment plan was built and tested in real conditions, dependencies of unproductive costs and route parameters were established using a mathematical model of the driver's work on the route. At the fourth stage, a hypothesis was put forward, a sectoral method of organizing the work of drivers was developed, a mathematical justification, a technical and organizational scheme

for organizing the work of drivers at a route passenger transport enterprise was presented and an optimization problem was formulated, its formalization was made and a solution based on optimization methods was proposed. At the fifth stage, the sectoral method was tried and introduced into the work of enterprises of route passenger transport in Belarus, feedback was received based on the results of the implementation, certain additions were made that were aimed at improving the developed method.

In order to obtain data for the study of the mode of use of drivers' working hours, the primary accounting documents of enterprises were analyzed in depth. Due to the fact that the daily duration of the driver's work is determined by the traffic schedule and is not constant, the mode of cumulative accounting of working hours is applied for drivers, for which it is mandatory to develop a work schedule for the accounting period.

Enterprises choose one month as the accounting period, which allows them to plan the work of drivers for the foreseeable period and calculate the duration of work with the payment of the amount due for overtime at the end of each month. Drivers' working hours are determined by the start and end time of each working day (shift), its duration, the start and end time of lunch breaks, breaks between parts of the working day, the number and order of working days and weekends in the accounting period. Thus, the work schedule is a document that sets the working hours of drivers.

By the nature of the distribution of the duration of the driver's work in the t_{sh} shift (on the example of a trolleybus company), according to the schedule for weekdays of the week, continuous shifts can be distinguished ($n = 235$; average = 7,9353; st. off = 1,646; max. = 10,9; min. = 3,78) and shifts with the division of the working day into parts ($n = 39$; average = 8,8562; st. off = 0,8381; max. = 10,23; min. = 7,15). On weekends of the week, only continuous shifts are provided, and the nature of their distribution differs from continuous shifts on working days ($n = 155$; average = 8,6035; art. off = 1,2297; max. = 10,72; min. = 5,43).

Histograms of the distribution of the duration of driver shifts are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 – Histograms of the distribution of the duration of drivers' shifts by continuous shifts (left) and by shifts with the division of the day into parts (right)

At the same time, the nature of the distribution of the duration of drivers' shifts also differs along different routes, as can be seen in the span diagrams shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 – Diagrams of the scope of the duration of shifts of drivers on various routes by continuous shifts (left) and by shifts with the division of the day into parts (right)

Taking into account the fact that drivers at enterprises are assigned to work on permanent routes, on which they work, with the exception of rare cases of unplanned rearrangements, it should be noted that the nature of their employment on this route, and, consequently, the nature of the use of their working time when working on the route differs significantly from route to route.

At the same time, the duration of the driver's working shift t_{sh} , set by the traffic schedule, can be represented as a model (1):

$$t_{sh} = t_{pt} + t_{ft} + t_{zib} + t_{zte} + n_{AB} (t_{AB} + t_{stmB}) + n_{BA} (t_{BA} + t_{stmA}) + t_{staA} + t_{staB}, \quad (1)$$

- where t_{pt} — preparatory time;
- t_{ft} — final time;
- t_{zib} — the duration of the zero trip at the beginning of the shift;
- t_{zte} — the duration of the zero trip at the end of the shift;
- n_{AB}, n_{BA} — number of trips in the direction of AB и BA;
- t_{AB}, t_{BA} — duration of trips in the direction of AB и BA;
- t_{stmA}, t_{stmB} — duration of mandatory parking at stations A и B;
- t_{staA}, t_{staB} — duration of optional parking at stations A и B.

the vehicle from the park, the return of the vehicle to the park, with the change of drivers on the line), the duration of t_{AB}, t_{BA} of the main trips in the AB and BA directions, the time required for their execution is determined, the duration of the stops t_{stmA}, t_{stmB} depends on the type of enterprise used, and the time of additional stops t_{staA}, t_{staB} at the terminal stations A and B, as well as the number of trips of the n_{AB}, n_{BA} are determined when drawing up a schedule and are dictated by the need for transportation. The largest share in the t_{sh} is the time used to perform surfactant, trips in the AB and BA directions (together making up the turnaround trips), respectively, the actual time of the t_{sh} will be determined to a greater extent by the time of the Fact of the turnaround trip. Figure 3 shows a diagram of the time span of the turnaround trip according to the schedule and the actual travel time, as well as a histogram of the distribution of the actual time of the turnaround trip.

Figure 3 – The span diagram for the turnaround time of the T_{shed} , established by the schedule and the actual time of the T_{actual} , (left) and the histogram of the T_{actual} distribution (right)

The values of t_{AB} , t_{BA} when scheduling differ by time of day, and the actual values of t_{AB} , t_{BA} , t_{zib} , t_{zte} , t_{staA} , t_{staB} are additionally influenced by a number of factors, including those of a random nature. The actual driving time has a normal distribution, and the deviations of the actual time of the T_{actual} from the time of the T_{shed} according to the traffic schedule are not significant and are mostly compensated by the time t_{staA} , t_{staB} additional parking, the actual values of t_{shed} will not have serious differences with the planned schedule time.

In the course of further research, clusters of drivers working on permanently fixed routes were identified, systematically having processing, despite the fact that drivers of other clusters have a defect (when determining processing, situations involving the occurrence of overtime hours caused by circumstances that were caused by abnormal situations or a systemic shortage of drivers were not taken into account). It becomes obvious that these facts depend on the modes of operation of the routes to which they are assigned (that is, on the routes themselves).

It should be added that according to the results of the work for the accounting period, the duration of working time exceeding the norm according to the republican labour calendar of the T_{lc} is paid by enterprise to the driver using an increasing coefficient of $k_{forc} \geq 2$ (the value is determined by the accepted wage system).

The mode of cumulative working time accounting allows the enterprise to flexibly take into account the actual time worked on the line by each driver (if it deviates from an 8-hour working day). Thanks to the mode of cumulative accounting of working hours, enterprises have the opportunity to compensate for shifts of longer duration on certain working days of the driver with shifts of shorter duration on other working days. This makes it possible, within each accounting period, to provide a total duration of working time not exceeding the duration of working time established according to the national production calendar for this calendar period. To ensure this condition, during the month, the company alternates drivers by route changes so that the total working time on a monthly basis is approximately equal for each of the drivers.

Taking into account the above, the hypothesis is put forward that the monthly working time of the driver T_i , working on a fixed fixed route, characterized by a set of $\{v_1; v_2; \dots; v_n\}$ of certain exits, each of which has

a working shift duration t_j , based on the condition of uniform alternation of each driver in shifts, can be determined using the dependence (2):

$$T_i = n_{wsh} \frac{n_{wd} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{wdei}} t_{wdij} + n_{sat} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{satei}} t_{satij} + n_{sun} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{sunei}} t_{sunij}}{n_{wd} n_{wdei} + n_{sat} n_{satei} + n_{sun} n_{sunei}}, (2)$$

where n_{wsh} is the number of working shifts of the driver in the accounting period;

n_{wd} , n_{sat} , n_{sun} — the number of working days, Saturdays and Sundays, respectively, in the period under review;

n_{wdei} , n_{satei} , n_{sunei} — the number of working shifts on the i -th route according to the schedule of working, Saturday and Sunday days, respectively;

t_{wdij} , t_{satij} , t_{sunij} — the duration of each j -th work shift on the i -th route according to the schedule of working days, Saturdays and Sundays, respectively.

At the same time, the second dependence multiplier (2) can be considered as an independent evaluation parameter (route characteristics). Therefore, it is advisable to introduce a criterion for the weighted average duration of the driver's working shift on the i -th route t_{avgri} , taking into account the mode of operation of the i -th route through the duration of working shifts on the route by days of the week, the number of working days, Saturdays and Sundays in the period under consideration, the value of which is determined by the formula (3):

$$t_{avgri} = \frac{n_{wd} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{wdei}} t_{wdij} + n_{sat} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{satei}} t_{satij} + n_{sun} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{sunei}} t_{sunij}}{n_{wd} n_{wdei} + n_{sat} n_{satei} + n_{sun} n_{sunei}}, (3)$$

To test the hypothesis put forward, an experiment was conducted, work schedules were investigated (the number of schedules is 2392, for a month with $n_{wsh}=20$ with $T_{lc}=160$), which are compiled for drivers working in continuous shifts assigned to permanent routes, based on the uniform alternation of shifts available on the fixed route between drivers (a scattering diagram is constructed based on the results, shown in Fig. 4).

Figure 4

Scattering diagram for monthly working hours when drivers work on a constant route with a given trsm

Taking into account that for other months, when changing the prsm (integer), results with similar scattering diagrams were obtained, the results obtained give reason to believe that in order to determine the monthly working time of drivers on a route when organizing its work with a given traffic schedule and known working shift durations, a mathematical model (1) can be used, and as a characteristic of the route — the t_{avgri} criterion [21].

At $T_i < T_{lc}$ drivers of the i -th route will have lack, while in fact the difference $(T_{lc} - T_i)$ is an unused resource of working time by the enterprise, and personally for each driver it is personal losses (lost wages that the driver did not have the opportunity to "earn").

Obviously, when $T_i > T_{lc}$ drivers of the i -th route will have processing paid for each $(T_i - T_{lc})$ hour of work using an increasing coefficient, which will form unproductive costs for enterprise.

Taking into account the above, the labor costs of the driver $C_{driveri}$ can be described using the dependence (4), which in the graph (Fig. 5) clearly shows the zone of occurrence of unproductive costs after reaching the inflection point of the $C_{driveri}$ at $T = T_{lc}$.

$$C_{driveri} = \begin{cases} T_i C_{hour}, & \text{when } T_i \leq T_{lc} \\ C_{hour} [T_i + (T_i - T_{lc})k_{forc}], & \text{when } T_i > T_{lc} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Figure 5 – The dependence of the driver's labor cost on T_i (left) and on t_{avgri} (right)

As a similar (3) characteristic for the entire enterprise, it makes practical sense to apply the criterion of the weighted average duration of the driver's work shift as a whole for the t_{avg} enterprise, the value of which is determined by (5):

$$t_{avg} = \frac{n_{wd} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{wde}} t_{wdj} + n_{sat} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{sate}} t_{satj} + n_{sun} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{sune}} t_{sunj}}{n_{wd}n_{wde} + n_{sat}n_{sate} + n_{sun}n_{sune}}, \quad (5)$$

where n_{wd} , n_{sat} , n_{sun} — the number of working days, Saturdays and Sundays, respectively, in the period under review;

n_{wdei} , n_{satei} , n_{sunei} — the number of working shifts on the enterprise according to the schedule of working, Saturday and Sunday days, respectively;

t_{wdij} , t_{satij} , t_{sunij} — the duration of each j -th work shift on the enterprise according to the schedule of working days, Saturdays and Sundays, respectively.

4. Developed sectoral method

A prerequisite for the organization of the work of passenger’s transport enterprise is compliance with the principle of social justice. Therefore, for each accounting period for the drivers of enterprise, it is proposed to establish an equal number of working shifts of provided for each of the drivers in this period, which should be determined using the t_{avg} , based on the time norm of the T_{lc} for the calendar period established by the republican production calendar, according to the formula (6):

$$n_{wsh} = \left\lfloor \frac{T_{lc}}{t_{avg}} + 0,5 \right\rfloor, \tag{6}$$

where T_{lc} — is the norm of time according to the national labour calendar, h;
 t_{avg} is the weighted average duration of the work shift on all routes.

Then the duration of the working time of the driver of the i -th route for the accounting period can be determined by the formula (7)

$$T_i = \left\lfloor \frac{T_{lc}}{t_{avg}} + 0,5 \right\rfloor \frac{n_{wd} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{wdei}} t_{wdij} + n_{sat} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{satei}} t_{satij} + n_{sun} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{sunei}} t_{sunij}}{n_{wd}n_{wdei} + n_{sat}n_{satei} + n_{sun}n_{sunei}}, \tag{7}$$

Taking into account the formulated condition for the occurrence of unproductive costs $T_i > T_{lc}$, the estimated value of unproductive costs C_{ovt} arising from the need to pay overtime in the amount of l_{ovt} for each hour of overtime for $n_{drivers}$ drivers of the i -th route can be determined by the formula (8):

$$C_{ovti} = \max \left(l_{ovt} n_{drivers} \left[\frac{T_{lc}}{t_{avg}} + 0,5 \right] \frac{n_{wd} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{wdei}} t_{wdij} + n_{sat} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{satei}} t_{satij} + n_{sun} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{sunei}} t_{sunij}}{n_{wd}n_{wdei} + n_{sat}n_{satei} + n_{sun}n_{sunei}} - T_{lc}; 0 \right) \tag{8}$$

On the other hand, it is possible to estimate the value of unproductive costs of Lxi using the formula (9):

$$C_{ovti} = \max \left(l_{ovt} n_{drivers} n_{wsh} t_{avgri} - T_{lc}; 0 \right) \cong \max \left(l_{ovt} n_{drivers} n_{wsh} \left[t_{avgri} - t_{avg} \right]; 0 \right) \tag{9}$$

In order to reduce the level of unproductive costs Lsu arising from the need to pay overtime, from (9) follows the objective need to minimize $\Delta_{ti} = t_{avgri} - t_{avg}$ with a constant timetable, l_{ovt} , $n_{drivers}$, etc. This model reduces to the task of minimizing the objective function Z using the dependence (10):

$$Z = \max \left(\frac{n_{wd} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{wdei}} t_{wdij} + n_{sat} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{satei}} t_{satij} + n_{sun} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{sunei}} t_{sunij}}{n_{wd}n_{wdei} + n_{sat}n_{satei} + n_{sun}n_{sunei}} - \frac{n_{wd} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{wde}} t_{wdj} + n_{sat} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{sate}} t_{satj} + n_{sun} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{sune}} t_{sunj}}{n_{wd}n_{wde} + n_{sat}n_{sate} + n_{sun}n_{sune}}; 0 \right) \rightarrow \min \tag{10}$$

To solve this problem, a sectoral method (SM) has been developed for organizing the work of drivers of the enterprise when working according to specified traffic schedules, characterized by the formation in each column (Fig. 6) enterprises sectors and assigning drivers not to routes, but to sectors, with the combination and alternation of routes within the sector so as to ensure uniform turnover (alternation) of drivers along the routes of the sector formed taking into account the criterion t_{avgri} of the weighted average duration of the driver's work on the routes of the sector, characterized by capacity, productivity, safety coefficient, type of required vehicle.

Figure 6 – Basic technical and production scheme of the organization of the company’s work before the use of CM (left), after the use of CM (right)

The basic principle of the sector is a weighted "commute switching" routes and "switching" drivers assigned to this sector. As a result, the sector is a controlled closed system "vehicle-driver-route-mode of operation", which has the ability to manage and monitor the state of individual elements of the sector with an operational analysis of efficiency, which makes it possible to identify and promptly solve problems arising within the sector [22].

Within the framework of the SM, the laws of the organization of the "vehicle-driver-route-mode of operation" system are valid: the isotropy of the duration of working time within the sector system, the preservation of equality of mileage within the sector system.

The main difference between the SM is that the work of the vehicle and its drivers is not organized along a permanent route, but along all routes included in the sector, therefore, such a decision increases the awareness of drivers about the specifics of traffic conditions on routes within the sector and awareness of typical road traffic situations arising on them.

The SM determines that each sector will meet the following requirements:

- complementarity (combining routes into a sector based on the commonality of significant parameters);
- scalability (the possibility of increasing the number of elements of the sector due to individual releases or routes based on taking into account significant criteria to ensure the stability of the properties of the sector);
- productivity (ensuring the required values of the efficiency of work);
- manageability (ensuring the possibility of both centralized and decentralized sector management, monitoring of the state of the sector, the possibility of effective management of the human resource of the sector, planning and development);
- readiness (the period of time for which work in the sector can be deployed);
- versatility (based on the interchangeability of vehicles and drivers);
- fault tolerance (the ability to quickly respond to the failure of individual elements of the sector);
- safety (the ability of the sector to ensure a high level of traffic safety by increasing the awareness of drivers about traffic conditions on routes inside the sector, the selection of drivers based on the driver safety rating and the safety rating of the sector, which is an

element of a proactive approach to ensuring traffic safety and transportation);

- reliability.

The possibility of using the SM to organize the work of the vehicle on the routes is to allocate and sector-specific routes with common segments, based on the rules of "switching" and combining routes within the sector, while maintaining the mandatory sequential alternation of work on them, rational distribution of driving and technical resources of the sector.

To implement the SM, a sector design methodology has been developed based on the assignment of such a combination of routes in the sector, which will implement the principle of ensuring an equivalent production load based on the t_{avgr} criterion, while additionally taking into account a number of criteria that affect the choice of combined routes (similarity of the route, the presence of a common terminal station where driver changes take place, the safety coefficient of the sector, route safety factor, etc.)

The task is original in that the division is carried out under the control of equality of the weighted average value of the shift duration in each formed sector with a number of restrictions with an unknown number of sectors and the number of shifts in them. The solution of the problem of sector formation is currently carried out by the expert method, calculations are carried out manually, which leads to a decrease in efficiency.

To formalize and solve the problem, we will take the following:

$\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n$ – a set of working hours corresponding to shifts 1, 2, ..., n;

b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n – a set of working hours corresponding to shifts ($b_i \in B = \{0,1\}$), corresponding to the "special shift" attribute;

m – the maximum allowed number of resulting vectors to be distributed over shifts, ($m \leq n$);

k – the minimum number of resulting vectors over which shifts should be distributed, ($1 < k \leq m$);

η_0 – the minimum allowable share of "special shifts" in the sector.

Let's introduce binary variables x_{ij} , $i = 1, \dots, m$, $j = 1, \dots, n$ (which can be viewed as a matrix $[x_{ij}]_{m \times n}$), and we will agree to interpret the meaning $x_{ij} = 1$ ($x_{ij} = 0$) as a sign of belonging (lack of belonging) j -shifts to i -sector. Then the partition problem can be represented as (1):

$$f([x_{ij}]_{m \times n}) = \max_{\substack{i_1, i_2 = 1, \dots, m, \\ i_1 \neq i_2, \\ \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j} \neq 0, \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j} \neq 0}} \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j} \tau_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j}} - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j} \tau_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j}} \right)^2 \rightarrow \min, \quad (1)$$

Where $x_{ij} \in B$

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^{m,n} x_{ij} = n \quad (C0) \text{ (the range of variable values)}$$

$$\sum_{\substack{i_1, i_2 = 1, \\ i_1 \neq i_2, \\ n}} x_{i_1 j} x_{i_2 j} = 0 \quad (C1) \text{ (the condition for maintaining the total number of shifts by sector),}$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} > 0, i = 1, \dots, k \quad (C2) \text{ (the condition for a shift belonging to only one sector),}$$

$$\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} b_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij}} \geq \eta_0, i = 1, \dots, m \quad (C3) \text{ (conditions for k non-empty sectors),}$$

$$(C4) \text{ (conditions for the minimum share of "special shifts" in the sector).}$$

To find a solution to this problem, it makes sense to turn to the theory of pseudo-Boolean functions (real-valued functions with arguments from B).

In accordance with the theory, if a pseudo-Boolean function is represented by a formula in which only the sums of the products of the arguments participate, then the minimum of such a function coincides with the minimum of the function given by the same formula, but in which the arguments are allowed to take values not only from B, but also from the segment $U=[0,1]$ (the extension of the function c B by U).

Since in the problem being solved, the function f and the constraints are "similar" to the specified form of the function assignment, taking into account the

$$f_{\varepsilon}([x_{ij}]_{m \times n}) = \max_{\substack{i_1, i_2=1, \dots, m, \\ i_1 \neq i_2}} \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j} \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j} \tau_j - \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j} \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j} \tau_j}{(\varepsilon + \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j})(\varepsilon + \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j})} \right)^2, \quad (2)$$

where ε — some sufficiently small positive number.

2. In order to make the objective function differentiable at all points (and thereby facilitate the application of optimization methods using derivatives), we approximate the operation of taking the maximum by the operation «LogSumExp», exactly, $\max\{a_1, \dots, a_r\} \rightarrow \frac{1}{\gamma} \ln(e^{\gamma a_1} + \dots + e^{\gamma a_r})$, where $\gamma > 0$ — the parameter responsible for the accuracy of the approximation (the higher γ , the more accurate the approximation). In addition, since the logarithm is a monotone function, it

$$f_{\varepsilon, \gamma}([x_{ij}]_{m \times n}) = \sum_{\substack{i_1, i_2=1, \\ i_1 < i_2}}^m \exp \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j} \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j} \tau_j - \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j} \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j} \tau_j}{(\varepsilon + \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j})(\varepsilon + \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j})} \right)^2 \rightarrow \min, \quad (3)$$

where $x_{ij} \in U$

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^{m,n} x_{ij} = n$$

$$\sum_{\substack{i_1, i_2=1, \\ i_1 < i_2}}^m x_{i_1 j} x_{i_2 j} = 0$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} > 0, i = 1, \dots, k$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} (b_j - \eta_0) \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, m$$

(C0) (the range of variable values)

(C1) (the condition for maintaining the total number of shifts by sector)

(C2) (the condition for a shift belonging to only one sector)

(C3) (conditions for k non-empty sectors),

(C4) (conditions for the minimum proportion of "special shifts" in the sector).

Such a problem can be solved, for example, by the internal point method ("interior point method"), although it should be expected that the solutions found will be local minima, and accordingly, to search for a global one, it may be necessary to run this method with different initial conditions (random search with interior point method).

5. Analysis and discussion

The study shows that the duration of working shifts within each route is not equal and varies widely by route releases (with a normal distribution). To characterize the route, the criterion of the weighted average duration of the driver's work shift t_{avgri} can be applied, the same criterion can be applied for the sector and for the enterprise as a whole. It is established that the large-

above, it makes sense to relax the original problem to the problem with the extension B to U and assume that the solution of this relaxed problem will coincide with the solution of the original problem. For the relaxed problem, in turn, numerical methods of real optimization are applicable.

Relaxation of the problem and preparation for numerical methods.

1. To avoid the need to select only the cases when searching for the maximum when calculating the function $f \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_1 j} \neq 0, \sum_{j=1}^n x_{i_2 j} \neq 0$, you can replace its expression with an expression of the form (2):

can be discarded altogether in order to simplify calculations for computational methods (the solution to the problem of finding the minimum of the objective function will not change);

3. To reduce the calculation for the sum in which summation is performed for all non-matching indexes i_1, i_2 , and the terms symmetric in the permutation of these indices are involved, it makes sense to limit ourselves only to the expression with summation by $i_1 < i_2$. Thus, we obtain the function (3):

est share of the driver's working time falls on the duration of the completed turnaround trips. The actual duration of the turnover trips of the vehicle carrying passengers on regular routes is investigated, the dependences of its change by time of day are established. It is determined that the actual value of the duration of the turnaround trip can be considered as having a normal distribution.

The driver's work, organized within the sector, can be described using a mathematical model that takes into account the number of working shifts and the weighted average duration of the work shift t_{avg} . The study shows that this mathematical model is applicable and has justified itself in practice.

On the basis of the SM, the development of work schedules for drivers and work orders for drivers is carried out, a computer program for the formation of sectors has been developed. The solution of the problem is implemented using the Wolfram Mathematica 13.2 system, includes a block of source data, constraints, setting the objective function and optimization criteria, directly optimization and output of calculation results. Finding the optimal value is implemented by the "Interior point" method with a limitation of the maximum number of iterations of 2000, the results of solving the optimization problem are presented in matrix form.

As a result of the performed calculation on the example of the tram enterprise at the given τ_i, b_i (see table), $m=4, k=3, \eta_0=0,33$ the division of shifts with the formation of two sectors, with weighted average durations of work in general by issues, was made 16,12 and 16,04 (one driver shift accounts for 8.06 hours and 8.02 hours for the first and second sectors, respectively) for each sector, respectively, with the proportion of "special shifts" 0.50 and 0.47 for the formed sectors.

Table.

Data on the duration of shifts on release τ_i with signs of a "special shift" b_i

i	$\tau_i, \text{ч}$	b_i	i	$\tau_i, \text{ч}$	b_i	i	$\tau_i, \text{ч}$	b_i	I	$\tau_i, \text{ч}$	b_i	i	$\tau_i, \text{ч}$	b_i	I	$\tau_i, \text{ч}$	b_i
1	19,55	0	7	18,5	0	13	17,68	0	19	16,83	1	25	14,15	1	31	11,4	1
2	19,06	0	8	18,45	0	14	17,41	0	20	15,83	1	26	13,31	1	32	11,05	1
3	19,05	0	9	18,33	0	15	17,38	0	21	15,78	1	27	13,25	1	33	10,63	1
4	18,98	0	10	18,31	0	16	17,18	0	22	15,61	1	28	12,19	1	–	–	–
5	18,92	0	11	18	0	17	17,14	0	23	14,78	1	29	12,15	1	–	–	–
6	18,67	0	12	17,82	0	18	16,87	1	24	14,67	1	30	11,43	1	–	–	–

Optimization calculations were performed on a computer with an Intel i5-3210M processor running Windows 10 with a calculation execution time of 297 s. It is worth noting that despite the fact that in the proposed approach, the number of variables for which optimization is performed grows as $m \times n$ (which theoretically, with large values of m and n , can significantly slow down the work on finding a solution by a method like "inner point"), nevertheless, it can be considered as quite practical, since in real enterprises, the typical values of m and n rarely exceed the values of 4 and 30, respectively.

6. Conclusions

To date, SM has been successfully implemented at six enterprises. The formation of sectors, the assignment of drivers to sectors (and not to individual routes) with the provision of uniform alternation of drivers between the releases of routes included in the sector, the formation of work schedules for drivers based on formalized sequences ensured an increase in the quality of operational work and a significant reduction in the level of unproductive costs.

SM balances, balances, harmonizes the monthly work schedule within the sector, balancing the mileage of the vehicle within the enterprise, minimizing the underwork and processing of individual drivers, thereby minimizing the level of unproductive costs associated with paying drivers overtime. It is worth noting that SM also provides a uniform mileage of vehicle.

Taking into account the fact that the work of vehicles and their drivers is organized not on a permanent route, but on routes entering the sector, drivers' awareness of the peculiarities of traffic conditions on the routes of the sector improves and the reliability of drivers increases.

References

1. Kapsky, D. & Sarazhinsky, D. & Semchenkov, S.. (2023). Approach to solving the problem of sector formation in organizing the work of drivers at the en-

terprises of route passenger transport based on pseudo-boolean optimization. Herald of Polotsk State University. Series B. Industry. Applied Sciences. 47. 77-81. 10.52928/2070-1616-2023-47-1-77-81.

2. Chen, Mingming & Niu, Huimin. (2012). A Model for Bus Crew Scheduling Problem with Multiple Duty Types. Discrete Dynamics in Nature and Society. 2012. 10.1155/2012/649213.

3. Drexl, M., Rieck, J., Sigl, T. et al. Simultaneous Vehicle and Crew Routing and Scheduling for Partial- and Full-Load Long-Distance Road Transport. Bus Res 6, 242–264 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03342751>

4. Ibarra-Rojas, O.J.; Delgado, F.; Giesen, R.; Muñoz, J.C. Planning, operation, and control of bus transport systems: A literature review. Transp. Res. Part B Methodol. 2015, 77, 38–75.

5. M. Salicrú, C. Fleurent, J.M. Armengol, Time-table-based operation in urban transport: Run-time optimisation and improvements in the operating process, Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice, Volume 45, Issue 8, 2011, Pages 721-740

6. Ibeas, A.; Alonso, B.; dell'Olivo, L.; Moura, J.L. Bus Size and Headways Optimization Model Considering Elastic Demand. J. Transp. Eng. 2014, 140, 370–380

7. Useche, S, Gómez V., Cendales B., Alonso F., 2018. Working Conditions, Job Strain, and Traffic Safety among Three Groups of Public Transport Drivers, Safety and Health at Work, Volume 9, Issue 4, 454-461. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2018.01.003>.

8. Przystupa, K., Gil, L., Niewczas, A., Pieniak, D., 2019. Working time of a Polish professional driver. Archives of Transport, 52(4), 57-66. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0014.0208>

9. Brunoro, Claudio & Sznelwar, Laerte & Bolis, Ivan & Abrahão, Júlia. (2015). The work of bus drivers and their contribution to excellence in public transportation. Production. 25. 323-335. 10.1590/0103-6513.114012.

10. Wong, J.Y.L., Gilson, N.D., Bush, R.A. and Brown, W.J. (2014), Patterns and perceptions of physical activity and sedentary time in male transport drivers working in regional Australia. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health*, 38: 314-320. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1753-6405.12214>
11. S Fores, L Proll & A Wren (2002) TRACS II: a hybrid IP/heuristic driver scheduling system for public transport, *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 53:10, 1093-1100, DOI: 10.1057/palgrave.jors.2601271
12. De Leone, Renato & Festa, Paola & Marchitto, Emilia. (2011). A Bus Driver Scheduling Problem: a new mathematical model and a GRASP approximate solution. *J. Heuristics*. 17. 441-466. 10.1007/s10732-010-9141-3.
13. Brunoro, Claudio et al. 'Contributions of Ergonomics to the Construction of Bus Drivers Health and Excellence in Public Transport and at Work'. 1 Jan. 2012: 30 – 35.
14. M Lezaun, G Pérez & E Sáinz de la Maza (2006) Crew rostering problem in a public transport company, *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 57:10, 1173-1179, DOI: 10.1057/palgrave.jors.2602088
15. Yindong Shen, Jingpeng Li, and Kunkun Peng An estimation of distribution algorithm for public transport driver scheduling. *International Journal of Operational Research* 2017 28:2, 245-262
16. Bauer, M., Dźwigoń, W., Richter M., 2021. Personal safety of passengers during the first phase Covid-19 pandemic in the opinion of public transport drivers in Krakow. *Archives of Transport*, 59(3), 41-55. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0015.0090>
17. Klapita, V.: Procesný manažment ako efektívny nástroj riadenia železničného dopravného podniku (Process management as an effective management tool of a railway transport company), In: *Svet dopravy*, 01/2022, ISSN 1338 – 9629, Available from: https://www.svetdopravy.sk/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Svet_dopravy_PDF_1_2022.pdf (viewed: 25 January 2023)
18. Bearzotti, L. et al.: The Event Management Problem in a Container Terminal. *Journal of applied research and technology*, Volume 11, Pages 95 – 102, Published II/2013, IDS No: 099HDI, ISSN: 1665-6423. DOI: 10.1016/S1665-6423(13)71518-9
19. Kováč, M.: Posúdenie účinnosti systému procesného riadenia v podmienkach železničných dopravných spoločností (Assessment of the effectiveness of the process management system in the conditions of railway transport companies). *Železničná doprava a logistika*. Žilina: Katedra železničnej dopravy. VII/2011, No 3., ISSN 1336-7943, Available from: <https://docplayer.net/7528243-Obsah-zeleznicna-doprava-a-logistika-elektronicky-odborny-casopis.html> (viewed: 04 February 2023).
20. Brockner, J. The process matters – Engaging and equipping people for success. Princeton University Press. Pg. 352. ISBN 9780691165059.
21. Semtchenkov, S. and Kapski, D. Reduction of unproductive costs of route passenger transport by the sectoral method, *Vestnik of Polotsk State University. Part B. Industry. Applied Sciences*, 45(3), 2022, pp. 85-90. ISSN 2710-3900 Available from: <https://journals.psu.by/industry/article/view/1235> (Viewed: 18 August 2022).
22. Semtchenkov, S. and Kapski, D. Development of rational work schedules for drivers of route passenger transport using the sectoral method. *Vestnik of Polotsk State University. Part B. Industry. Applied Sciences*, 46(10), 2022 pp. 64-72. ISSN 2710-3900 Available from: <https://journals.psu.by/industry/article/view/1582> (viewed: 01 September 2022).